

Human Resource Practices and Organizational Citizenship Behavior Development

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Abstract

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) has been reported to give an organization competitive advantage. Employees who are ready to go an extra mile will increase the productivity of an organization. The aim of this study was to determine the impact of HR practices on the development of OCB. This study was conducted in two organizations namely: Delmonte Kenya Ltd. and Nampak Kenya Ltd. 243 respondents formed the sample of the study. The study adopted descriptive research design. A significant positive correlation was found between recruitment and selection and training and development and OCB. OCB was found to explain 55.9% of the variation in between recruitment and selection and training and development. It is recommended that managers should invest more in recruitment and selection and training and development in order to increase development of OCB.

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I. Introduction

Organizational citizenship behavior simply refers to the willingness of a worker to go an extra mile in an organization. It also refers to an employee's readiness to help others in an organization and the willingness to attend to duties outside their formal job description. Simply put, it shows the extent to which an employee can move out of his way for the good of the organization and colleagues. Organizational citizenship behavior has immense benefits in an organization. The most important of these is an organization enjoying increased productivity. Such an organization consequently increases its market share which is the dream of every manager.

Human resource management practices have been thought to either enhance or hinder the development of organizational citizenship behavior. Two practices particularly stand out. These are recruitment and selection and training and development

II. Objectives of the Study

General objective

The general objective was to determine the impact of human resource management practices on the development of organizational citizenship behavior.

Specific Objectives

1. To examine the influence of recruitment and selection on the development of organizational citizenship behavior.
2. To establish the effect of training and development on the development of organizational citizenship behavior.

Justification

OCB has been said to give firms competitive advantage and consequently improved productivity. Development of OCB has largely been attributed to the human resource practices an organization embraces.

III. Literature review

Theoretical framework

Social Exchange Theory

The social exchange theory proposes that employees show positive or negative behavior as a response to the treatment they receive from their employers. A strong social exchange relationship between the employer and employee will help maintain positive working relationships which in turn will move employees to engage themselves in OCB. As such, employers need to treat their employees fairly such that they can reciprocate the good gesture in the form of behavior such as organizational citizenship behavior which contributes to achieving more significant goals (Veličkovska, 2017).

The Psychological Contract Theory

A psychological contract represents an exchange relationship wherein two parties trade things of value. The psychological contract theory explains a two-way exchange process of perceived promises and obligations between employees and their employers. According to Armstrong (2006), the theory holds that employees expect to be treated fairly as human beings and to be rewarded equitably according to their contribution. Meeting the expectations of employees is likely to lead to the development of OCB.

Impression Management Theory

According to this theory, OCB is seen as part of employees' attempts to influence the images others have of them. Bolino (2008) posits that OCB is spurred by strategic reasons as employees seek to improve their future prospects in the organization.

Expectancy Theory

The expectancy theory was propagated by Victor Vroom in 1964. Expectancy is the belief that action or effort will lead to an outcome. An individual's behavior is affected by the degree to which the individual believes the outcomes to be possible. This affects development of OCB.

Organizational citizenship behavior

Organ (2005), defines organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as a discretionary individual behavior that promotes the effective functioning of an organization, even though it is not outrightly recognized by the formal reward system. Five specific categories of discretionary behavior identified are altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy and civic virtue (Organ, 1988). OCB therefore refers to a situation where an individual goes beyond his/her job description and does not expect anything in return. Volunteering for extra job activities, helping coworkers, and making positive comments about the company are some examples of OCB at the workplace (Luthans, 2011). Bolino and Turnley (2003) opined that the ability of an organization to cultivate and to manage citizenship behavior among employees is a key asset for the organization.

OCB has certain benefits to an organization. According to Chattopadhyay (2017), when the employees perform beyond their stipulated job description, such efforts lead to excellence in organizational performance. Organizational citizenship behavior has become popular because it gives an organization competitive advantage.

Human resource management practices

HRM practices are the processes that are developed and executed specifically to perceive a form of enhanced performance and superior competitive basis (Ulrich, 1997; Noe, 2015). Such practices are used by organizations to manage their employees through the developing specific competencies and generation of organization knowledge which help to sustain competitive advantage (Nikolett & Nawangsari, 2019). Good HRM practices have been reported to influence OCB positively. Consequently, increasing good HRM practices will increase the OCB and which means that the employees will happily do their job outside their main job (Harsasi, Muzammil & Radeswandri, 2017).

Recruitment and selection

According to Noor et al. (2013), recruitment and selection is a critical practice in helping organizations to manage OCB. A positive behavior in recruitment and selection will enable an organization to select the best talented employees that are best suited for the organization (Ahmed, 2016).

Vlachos (2008) observed that recruitment and selection gives the organization an ability to attract the right people with the requisite characteristics in terms of knowledge, practice and tactic.

Training and development

According to (Ahmad, 2011), training and development motivates employees to bring about more citizenship behavior. Training and development impart employees with skills, knowledge and attitudes to function responsibly (Guest, 2000). Equipping employees with the skills they require is an important prerequisite for OCB. The more skills employees possess, the better the quality and depth of OCB. Consequently, employees who attend more training and development programs are likely to perform better. They are also likely to be more confident, open to change and supportive of each other (Donovan, Hannigan & Crowe, 2001). Investing in employees' training improves their level of conscientiousness (Ahmad, 2011).

Several past studies have been conducted on the effect of training and development on employee's attitude and behaviour. Results of the studies indicate that training and development positively affects development of OCB in an organization (Ashill, Carruthers & Krisjanous, 2006; Tsaur & Lin, 2004; Tang &

Tang, 2012). Training and development programs help new employees adapt quickly to entry experiences resulting in lower feeling of uncertainty (Autry & Wheeler, 2005; Simosi, 2010). Fajar and Soeling (2017) and Ahmad (2011) found that training is significantly positively correlated with OCB. This implies that if organizations desire to increase the level of OCB of their employees, they should invest more in training their workers. They could be done by giving employees sufficient opportunities to improve themselves through training. Training should be conducted in suitable and comfortable places. All this will improve their overall OCB.

Hypotheses of the study

The following hypotheses guided the study:

1. H₀: There is no significant effect of recruitment and selection on OCB development
2. H₀: There is no significant effect of training and development on OCB development.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive research design. A sample of 243 respondents was drawn from Delmonte Kenya Limited and Nampak Kenya Limited.

IV. Findings And Discussions

Correlations

Table 1: Correlations

		OCBD	TND	RNS
OCBD	Pearson Correlation	1	.673**	.632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	243	243	243
TND	Pearson Correlation	.673**	1	.528**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	243	243	243
RNS	Pearson Correlation	.632**	.528**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	243	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows that there is a significant moderate positive correlation (r = 0.673; p-value <0.001) between training and development and OCB. Hypothesis H₀₁ is therefore rejected and conclude that training and development has a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior development. The table also shows there is a significant moderate positive correlation (r = 0.632; p-value <0.001) between recruitment and selection and OCB. Hypothesis H₀₂ is rejected and conclude that recruitment and selection have a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior development. These findings are similar to those found by Fajar and Soeling (2017) and Ahmad (2011).

Table 2: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	52.771	2	26.386	151.979	.000 ^b
	Residual	41.667	240	.174		
	Total	94.439	242			

- a. Dependent Variable: OCBD
- b. Predictors: (Constant), TND, RNS

Table 3: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.263	.150		8.412	.000
	RNS	.340	.045	.383	7.598	.000
	TND	.333	.036	.470	9.322	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OCBD

Y= β₀+β₁ X₁+ β₂ X₂+ ε
 Y= Organizational Citizenship Behaviour
 X₁=Training and development
 X₂=Recruitment and selection

β_0 = a constant which denotes organization Citizenship Behavior that is independent of HR practices
 β_1 & β_2 = intercepts for the independent variable
 ϵ =Error term

Under the model $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \epsilon$, the model was found to be valid ($F(2,240) = 151.979$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$) as indicated in Table 2. The fitted model equation is: $Y = 1.263 + 0.340X_1 + 0.333X_2 + \epsilon$

The model equation shows that standardized OCB will increase by 0.340 units with one unit increase in standardized reward management keeping the other variables constant. Standardized OCB will increase by 0.333 units with an increase of one unit in standardized performance management, keeping the other variables constant.

The regression results of training and development and recruitment and selection against OCB are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.748 ^a	.559	.555	.41667

a. Predictors: (Constant), TND, RNS

Table 4 shows that training and development and recruitment and selection explain 55.9% of the variation in OCB. Therefore, 44.1% of the variation in OCB is explained by factors outside the model. This shows that training and development and recruitment and selection (HR practices) significantly affect organizational citizenship behavior development. These results are in agreement with results obtained by Guyo (2015).

Implications for managers

The findings show that managers should be greatly concerned about employee training and development and recruitment and selection. There is need for training and development to be taken seriously. Adequate resources should be set apart for this purpose. There is need to conduct training needs assessment before embarking on training. This will make the training to be more meaningful and strategic. The employees should be involved at every stage right from the preparation stage all the way to the evaluation of the training. Adequately trained employees are likely to be ready to go an extra mile because they have the requisite knowledge and skills and are confident. A poorly equipped employee may shy off because they do not want to be disappointed or even to have their inadequacies publicly known. Training can also directly be used to sensitize employees on the importance of organizational citizenship.

Recruitment and selection should be carefully planned and rigorous so as to ensure that the best candidates are finally selected. Enough resources should be channeled towards this exercise because quality employees give an organization competitive advantage. Fairness should be seen to take center stage. If recruitment and selection is properly done, it may be possible to predict an employee's extent of organizational citizenship behavior in his/her working life.

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